

FIBER WAVINESS IN THERMOPLASTIC CFRP: MECHANISMS OF FORMATION AND MECHANICAL INFLUENCE

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTPs) have been increasingly applied, particularly in the aerospace field, due to their high productivity and recyclability. However, various molding defects caused by complex molding behaviors and high processing temperatures have hindered their application to critical structural components. Among these, in-plane fiber waviness on the surface of component surfaces is known to reduce longitudinal strength and induce complex damage propagation behavior. While numerous studies have investigated the geometric characteristics of fiber waviness and its influence on mechanical performance, the effects of process-induced phenomena during molding, especially crystallization behavior in thermoplastics, remain largely unexplored. This study aims to develop a numerical analysis framework that captures the entire process, from molding to mechanical performance of fiber waviness, incorporating the effects of the crystallization behavior of thermoplastics during the forming process. The validity of the proposed method is assessed through comparison with experiments, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of residual stresses and their influence on the mechanical performance of CFRTPs with fiber waviness.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, as the application of carbon fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRP) components in aerospace structures has advanced, there has been a growing demand not only for their excellent mechanical properties but also for additional functional innovations, such as recyclability or manufacturing productivity. In response, significant efforts have been directed toward the development of carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTPs), which use thermoplastic matrices that solidify upon cooling and can be re-melted upon heating. Owing to these characteristics, CFRTPs have attracted considerable attention as recyclable and highly productive materials. However, the high flowability of thermoplastic resins and the elevated processing temperature required during molding pose challenges, resulting in various manufacturing defects that continue to hinder the widespread application of CFRTPs to structural components.

Among these defects, fiber waviness caused by misalignment of fiber orientation is one of the most critical issues [1]. In CFRTP laminates, fiber waviness typically occurs in the in-plane direction of the surface, inducing inhomogeneous stress fields that lead to a reduction in mechanical strength and the emergence of complex fracture modes. These issues are further compounded by the relatively high processing temperatures and crystallization behavior characteristics of thermoplastic matrices, which are known to generate substantial residual strain during molding and cooling [2]. Notably, CFRTPs employed in structural components primarily utilize semicrystalline thermoplastic resins as their matrix

materials, which exhibit distinct crystallization behavior that significantly influences the development of residual strain. While the influence of fiber waviness on mechanical properties has been widely investigated through various numerical analysis methods [3-5], the potential impact of process-induced residual strains on fiber waviness and structure strength has raised increasing concern. Nevertheless, only a limited number of studies have incorporated the effects of molding-induced residual strain into numerical simulations.

Numerous experimental studies have explored the mechanisms of fiber waviness formation in CFRP laminates [6]. Among the various types of fiber waviness, in-plane fiber waviness occurring on the laminate surfaces is known to result from the interaction of multiple factors. Kugler et al. [7] identified key factors, such as tool plate/part coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) mismatch, temporal temperature gradients, and spatial temperature gradients through comparative investigations of amorphous CFRTPs. Krämer et al. [8] conducted real-time observations of crystalline CFRTPs and revealed the effects of molding conditions on fiber waviness formation. However, the influence of the parameters of molding conditions on fiber waviness formation and the effects on the mechanical properties of CFRTP laminates remain unclear.

This study proposes a numerical analysis framework to investigate the effects of molding conditions on in-plane fiber waviness in CFRTP laminates, with a particular focus on geometric characteristics and mechanical behavior. By comparing numerical simulation results with experimental data, the validity of the proposed approach is evaluated, and the influence of residual stresses generated around the fiber waviness on component strength is examined. This research establishes a link between molding conditions and the structural performance of CFRTP components, thereby contributing to the advancement of forming technologies for CFRTPs.

2 EXPERIMENT

MCCP1223 (CF/PA6 based unidirectional prepreg, Maruhachi Co.) is used as the material in this study. To intentionally induce in-plane fiber waviness through longitudinal compression during molding, A5052 aluminum molds with intentionally poor release agent coverage near the edges are employed, as illustrated in Figure 1. The release agent failure localizes the constraint during the cooling process, promoting localized compressive stress and fiber buckling (see Figure 1). A unidirectional 6-ply laminate (0° stacking) of 200×200 mm is prepared, with a total thickness of approximately 1 mm. The laminate is heated and pressed at 280°C and 1 MPa for 15 minutes.

Three different cooling conditions were applied: Slow cooling (in the hot press), Medium cooling (at room temperature), and Fast cooling (using water). Two laminates were molded under each condition. The average cooling rate between 250°C and 200°C was defined as the representative cooling rate: Slow (0.02 K/s), Medium (2.06 K/s), and Fast (24.30 K/s).

After molding, the geometric shape of the fiber waviness is measured using an optical microscope (see Figure 2). Furthermore, mechanical performance is evaluated using four-point bending tests (according to JIS K7074) and tensile tests (according to JIS K7165), with ten specimens tested for each cooling condition ($n = 10$). Load–displacement curves are used to determine the mechanical strength of the specimens, and the failure modes are identified through post-fracture observations of the tested specimens.

Figure 1: Formation mechanism of fiber waviness in CFRTP laminates

Figure 2: Optical microscopic images of fiber waviness

3 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS METHOD

3.1 Molding analysis

According to Kugler et al. [7], the primary mechanisms responsible for fiber waviness formation in amorphous CFRTPs include tool plate/part CTE mismatch, temporal temperature gradients, and spatial temperature gradients. Furthermore, in a study on crystalline CFRTPs, Krämer et al. [8] reported that fiber waviness forms during the cooling process within the temperature range between the processing temperature T_{\max} and the crystallization temperature T_c , referred to as the waviness formation temperature interval $\Delta T_w = T_{\max} - T_c$. It was also found that the width of this interval ΔT_w significantly affects the severity of the fiber waviness. Since both the waviness formation temperature interval ΔT_w and the crystallization behavior of thermoplastics are highly dependent on the cooling rate, this study treats the cooling rate as a key molding parameter and investigates its influence on the mechanical characteristics of fiber waviness.

Considering the above findings and the molding characteristics of crystalline thermoplastics, the fiber waviness formation process can be modeled in the following three stages:

- (i) Molten phase (Processing temperature T_{\max} to crystallization temperature T_c):
This stage is governed by the fluidity of the thermoplastic matrix.
- (ii) Solidification phase (Crystallization temperature T_c to glass transition temperature T_g):
The solidification of the matrix and the generation of residual stresses are considered.
- (iii) Solid phase (Glass transition temperature T_g to room temperature T_r):
The matrix is assumed to behave as a fully elastic material.

- (i) Molten phase (Processing temperature $T_{\max} \sim$ crystallization temperature T_c)

Above the crystallization temperature T_c , thermoplastics exhibit fluid-like behavior. Therefore, axial compressive stress acting on the fibers due to differential thermal shrinkage between mold and laminate is considered the primary cause of fiber waviness formation. Based on this assumption, the difference in shrinkage between the mold and the laminate during the cooling process is presumed to correspond to the amount of longitudinal shrinkage caused by the formation of fiber waviness.

The difference in thermal strain between the fiber and the mold ε_t can be expressed as:

$$\varepsilon_t = -(\alpha_t - \alpha_f)\Delta T_w, \quad (1)$$

where α_t and α_f are the CTE of mold and fiber. Based on the experimental observations, the geometric shape of fiber waviness is fitted to be sinusoidal as:

$$Y(x, y, z) = 2A_0(z) \cos^2(\pi y/2U) \cos^2(\pi x/\lambda) \quad (2)$$

$$A_0(z) = \begin{cases} A_0^{\max} z & (\text{under compression}) \\ A_0^{\max} & (\text{under tensile}) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where x, y : in-plane fiber direction and transverse direction, respectively; z : out-of-plane direction. A_0^{\max} : maximum amplitude; λ : wavelength; U : width of the waviness region (Figure 3). The strain caused by the fiber waviness ε_w is then given by:

Figure 3: Geometry of fiber waviness

$$\varepsilon_w = \ln \left(\lambda / \int_{-\lambda/2}^{\lambda/2} \sqrt{1 + (\partial Y / \partial x|_{y=0})^2} dx \right). \quad (4)$$

Since fiber waviness is generated locally in CFRTP laminates, the relationship between ε_t and ε_w can be described using the length subjected to axial fiber compression L_t and the length of the waviness region L_w :

$$L_t \varepsilon_t = L_w \varepsilon_w. \quad (5)$$

From Equations (1) to (5), the crystallization temperature T_c can be associated with the resulting geometric shape of the fiber waviness. Since T_c is significantly affected by the cooling rate, this establishes a direct relationship between the cooling rate and the geometric characteristics of fiber waviness. The stiffness of the thermoplastics is sufficiently low, and thus, the residual stress generated during this process is assumed to be negligible.

(ii) Solidification phase (Crystallization temperature T_c to glass transition temperature T_g):

Below the crystallization temperature T_c , it becomes necessary to consider the residual stresses generated during the cooling process due to the increase in matrix stiffness. In thermoplastics, shrinkage during the cooling process can be broadly classified into two categories: thermal shrinkage, caused by reduced molecular mobility with decreasing temperature, and crystallization shrinkage, resulting from the formation of crystalline structures. An incremental linear elasticity (ILE) model [9,10], which employs representative material properties in segments, introduced, is introduced to implement these effects of thermal shrinkage in numerical analysis.

Crystallization kinetics are modeled using the Ziabicki–Nakamura equation [11,12], a non-isothermal crystallization model:

$$\tilde{\theta}(t) = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\int_0^t K(T) dt \right)^n \right], \quad (6)$$

$$K(T) = K_{\max} \exp \left[\frac{-4 \ln 2 (T - \bar{T})^2}{D^2} \right], \quad (7)$$

where $\tilde{\theta}(t)$: the relative degree of crystallinity with respect to the maximum degree of crystallinity at time t , $K(T)$: the crystallization rate constant at temperature T , n : the Avrami index representing the fractal dimension of the crystals, and K_{\max} , \bar{T} , D : fitting parameters in the Gaussian approximation of the crystallization rate.

In this study, it is assumed that the mechanical properties of the thermoplastic matrix are proportional to its degree of crystallinity. The total shrinkage strain is considered to consist of two components: thermal shrinkage, which is proportional to the temperature change, and crystallization shrinkage, which is proportional to the degree of crystallinity. The magnitude of the crystallization shrinkage strain is estimated based on the warpage deformation in asymmetric laminates with a [0/90/90] stacking sequence, according to reference [13].

(iii) Solid phase (Glass transition temperature T_g to room temperature T_r)

Since no further crystallization is assumed to occur below the glass transition temperature T_g , the mechanical properties of the matrix are considered constant. Therefore, only the effects of thermal shrinkage are considered in this process. Finally, the demolding process is modeled by imposing a stress-free boundary condition on the model.

3.2 Strength analysis

Around the fiber waviness, complex damage behavior can arise due to the combined effects of the geometric shape of the fiber waviness and applied load conditions. To investigate this phenomenon, a high-fidelity numerical approach is introduced, in which fiber- and matrix-dominated damage mechanisms are modeled separately.

In fiber-dominated damage, it is well known that distinct failure mechanisms occur under longitudinal compressive and tensile loading. Under compressive loading, inhomogeneous shear stress fields arising from the initial fiber misalignment trigger the shear yielding of the matrix, leading to the formation of kink bands. In this study, the LaRC03 failure criterion [14], which accounts for fiber misalignment, is introduced for the onset of kink band. In addition, the physical based model (PBM) [15,16] is implemented to represent energy dissipation due to matrix plastic deformation. Under tensile loading, brittle damage associated with fiber fracture progresses, with failure initiation occurring randomly. This introduces a size effect, which is addressed in this study using the Weibull failure criterion [17].

In matrix-dominated damage, it is essential to capture displacement discontinuities caused by matrix cracking. In CFRP laminates, matrix cracks typically propagate along the fiber direction and can exhibit complex geometries. To efficiently model this cracking behavior, this study employs the extended finite element method (XFEM) [18,19], which allows for the representation of displacement discontinuities independently of the mesh geometry. Furthermore, to capture the plastic zone around the crack tip, a cohesive zone model (CZM) [20] is incorporated in conjunction with XFEM.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Simulation conditions

Numerical simulations are performed under three different cooling conditions: Slow (0.02 K/s), Medium (2.06 K/s), and Fast (24.30 K/s), in accordance with the experimental setup. The influence of cooling conditions on the geometric shape of the fiber waviness and its mechanical effects are investigated.

The dimensions of the finite element model are shown in Figure 4. Since fiber waviness forms continuously on the surface of the component, a representative volume element (RVE) with periodic boundary conditions is used as the analysis domain. In the four-point bending analysis, macroscopic curvature is applied, and the analysis is terminated when a 5% load drop is observed. In the tensile test simulation, macroscopic in-plane strain is applied, and the analysis is terminated when the Weibull failure criterion is satisfied. Structural strength is evaluated based on the surface stress of the RVE at the termination point of each analysis.

Figure 4: Finite element model and its dimensions

4.2 Experimental and simulation results

The effect of the cooling rate on the geometric characteristics of fiber waviness is shown in Figure 5. The vertical axis represents the severity of waviness, which is commonly used as a geometric metric of fiber waviness and is defined as:

$$w = A_0^{\max}/\lambda. \quad (8)$$

The simulation results show reasonable agreement with experimental data. These results indicate that the severity of fiber waviness increases with higher cooling rates. This is because higher cooling rates lead to lower crystallization temperature, thereby widening the waviness formation temperature interval ΔT_w in which fiber waviness forms. However, it should be noted that the Fast cooling condition exceeds the validated range of the cooling rate range of the DSC device (DSC 8500, Perkin Elmer Co.) used in the measurements of crystallization temperature, and further investigation is required.

Figure 6 presents both experimental and numerical results for the dependence of compressive and tensile strength on cooling rate. The vertical axis indicates the normalized strength obtained by dividing the measured or simulated strength by the reference strength of a specimen without fiber waviness. The numerical results show good agreement with the experimental data. Additionally, simulation results without residual stresses are included in Figure 6 to assess the effect of residual stresses on the mechanical behavior associated with fiber waviness. These results indicate that residual stresses generated around the fiber waviness region contribute to an increase in compressive strength while causing a reduction in tensile strength.

In the next section, the effects of the residual stress fields induced around the fiber waviness on the mechanical properties and the underlying mechanisms are discussed.

Figure 5: Cooling rate-dependent waviness geometry

(a) Compressive strength

(b) Tensile strength

Figure 6: Cooling rate-dependent structural strength

4.3 Discussion

The residual stresses around the fiber waviness contribute to an increase in compressive strength while leading to a reduction in tensile strength. This behavior is closely related to the dominant damage mechanisms occurring near the fiber waviness.

Under compressive loading, kink bands and matrix cracks are initiated around the fiber waviness due to localized shear stress, ultimately resulting in failure (Figure 7). In contrast, under tensile loading, matrix cracking caused by localized shear stress induces stress concentration, which subsequently leads to fiber breakage (Figure 8). As shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10, the residual shear stress field generated by fiber waviness acts in the opposite direction to the shear stress field induced under compressive loading but in the same direction as that induced under tensile loading. This observation suggests that the residual stress field helps to suppress damage under compressive loading while it facilitates damage initiation under tensile loading.

Among the three cooling conditions, the residual shear stress field is found to be most pronounced under the slow cooling condition. Although both the geometric nonlinearity of fiber waviness and the magnitude of matrix shrinkage during cooling contribute to the development of the residual shear stress field, the results indicate that matrix shrinkage has a more dominant influence.

Considering the residual stresses, the simulation results for the Medium and Fast cooling conditions show good agreement with the experimental data. However, this is not the case for the Slow condition. The proposed analysis approach does not account for time-dependent effects in the resin, such as the relaxation of residual stresses. Therefore, the development of numerical methods capable of capturing these effects is needed in future work.

Slow

Fast

(a) Experimental observation

(b) Simulation (Fast cooling rate)

Figure 7: Fracture mode under compressive loading

(a) Experimental observation

(b) Simulation (Fast cooling rate)

Figure 8: Fracture mode under tensile loading

Figure 9: Residual shear stress around fiber waviness

Figure 10: Shear stress field around fiber waviness
(Left: Under compressive loading $K = 0.01$, Right: Under tensile loading $E = 0.01$)

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, a numerical analysis framework is developed to investigate the relationship between molding conditions, specifically cooling rate, and the geometric and mechanical characteristics of in-plane fiber waviness in CFRTPL laminates. The proposed method incorporates a process-dependent residual stress formulation based on the crystallization behavior of semicrystalline thermoplastics and evaluates its influence on mechanical performance through comparison with experimental data.

The results demonstrated that higher cooling rates lead to more severe fiber waviness due to a wider waviness formation temperature interval associated with a lower crystallization temperature. The severity of fiber waviness is found to significantly affect both compressive and tensile strength, and the proposed simulation framework showed good agreement with experimental results under Medium and Fast cooling conditions.

Residual stresses generated around the fiber waviness region are shown to enhance compressive strength by offsetting the externally applied shear stress field, while they promoted failure under tensile loading due to reinforcement of the local stress field. These mechanisms were validated by both experimental observations and simulation results.

However, discrepancies between simulation and experiment under the Slow cooling condition highlight the limitations of the current framework, which does not account for time-dependent effects such as residual stress relaxation during slow cooling. Future work should focus on incorporating viscoelastic behavior and long-term stress relaxation models into the process simulation in order to further improve the accuracy and predictive capability of fiber waviness modeling in CFRTPLs.

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